

OVERCOMING PRAGMATIC PROBLEMS IN THE PROCESS OF SIMULTANEOUS TRANSLATION

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ANNOTATSIYA

The article is devoted to investigation of the specifics of simultaneous interpretation as a top of the translation skills, which determines high demands to the level of development of translation competence. The subject of research is the study of modern approaches to the classification of errors that occur in the simultaneous interpreting activity. The aim of the research are: 1) an investigation of the causes and mechanisms which lead to appearance of the errors in the implementation of practical translation work of a simultaneous interpreter; 2) an analysis of modern approaches to the classification of possible translation errors.

The processes of mutual understanding between representatives of various cultural models can be significantly complicated by the implementation of an erroneous interpretation of certain connotations of the original, due to translation errors, which are especially possible in simultaneous translation, based on the need to instantly respond to the information heard, without being able to think over the details.

The issues of classification and identification of the causes of errors in simultaneous translation is one of the most important problems of translation management, the solution of which will avoid erroneous interpretation of one or another information in the language of the host culture, ensure the equivalence and adequacy of the translation, which

determines the relevance of the selected research topic.

The object of the research is translation errors that occur during simultaneous translation.

The purpose of the study is to identify some errors in the process of simultaneous translation.

Simultaneous translation (SP) is one of the most difficult types of translation activities. In modern scientific literature, SP is understood as "one of the types of oral translation, simultaneous translation of the spoken text, one of the types of professional translation", "the pinnacle of translation art". At its core, SP is a psychological process in which three main stages are distinguished: understanding, comprehension and formation of a concept,

transmission, reproduction by means of the language system of the receiving cultural model.[1]

The first stage of translation activity, namely the perception of a foreign language text, is a complex sensory-thinking process, which is based on the simultaneous execution of the analytical and synthetic functions of the brain and sense organs. Comprehension is carried out with the help of the formation and formulation of thought, that is, with the help of internal speech. The main question is, by means of which language is the understanding carried out and how high is the degree of intensification of its course. The highest degree presupposes the obligatory language design of thought. As for linguistic means, comprehension can be carried out by means of the original language, or with a high level of proficiency in this type of speech activity - in the target language, and with high skill of the translator - with the help of means of an internal individual subject-schematic semantic code.

The second stage of the translation process is the formation of the main meaning of the future message. In other words, at this stage there is a need to comprehend the relationship "meaning - idea", as well as re-coding. If comprehension is carried out in the target language, then the formation of meaning is simultaneously and the formation of an idea, and the process of thinking itself includes the process of recoding [4]. In this case, the recoding process is not recognized, since it is highly automated.

At the third, final stage of translation activity, the utterance is displayed and recreated using the means of the target language. The attributive, essential characteristics of the joint venture put

forward high requirements for the level of formation of translation competence, which today is most often understood as a set of specific skills required by a member of the linguistic community for verbal contacts with others. The lists of the distinguished skills of different authors do not coincide and are not clearly marked for all of them, which is associated with an objectively large number of these skills and the lack of their correct hierarchization.[2]

The reasons for the occurrence of linguistic errors can be attributed to the desire for hypercorrection - "erroneous grammatical use associated with the excessive implementation of the desired rule"; implementation of speech behavior by analogy with the norms of the native language. All lexical and grammatical errors can be classified according to stylistic and social nature. In the process of a detailed analysis of the most common mistakes, A.S. Barmina points out that all deviations from the norm can be classified "depending on what aspect of the language they relate to, as well as the nature of the complexity and frequency of this error in various language registers". The researcher singles out errors of the first and second categories: the errors of the first category include "elementary" errors characteristic of people without higher education. Errors of the second category include. There are "mistakes of the middle style, typical of most educated people", widely used in publications devoted to the normalization of modern English, dictionaries of difficulties, and so on. In turn, M.A. Kunilovskaya, on the basis of a detailed analysis of the classifications presented in domestic and foreign translation studies, at the top level of taxonomy, distinguishes semantic and linguistic errors, and semantic

errors distort the semantics of the original much more significantly than expression errors.

Semantic errors can be classified according to the type of unchanged or non-transmitted information, according to the degree of deviation from the original, misleading effect on the recipient. Taking this criterion into account, M.A.Kunilovskaya distinguishes the following types of semantic errors:

- errors with the transfer of referential information caused by an incorrect vision of the behind-text reality. Such errors can lead to an indication of other referents, reference situations, significantly distorting the semantics of the original. The same group includes errors associated with the representation of predicative information, including incorrect transmission of species-temporal, modal values, errors in the transmission of proper names.

It is advisable to use state private enterprise mechanisms to support agricultural producers. Lease financing is an effective

tool for increasing the competitiveness of agricultural producers. The competitiveness of domestic agricultural producers is largely determined by their technical equipment.[3]

In the practice of foreign countries, it has become an international practice where the crimes of bribery of officials are widespread. In some countries, it was even possible to get deductions from your company's tax liabilities in exchange for bribes, and this is not surprising, as multinational corporations around the world have already paid bribes to support their businesses. [4]

An example of the appearance of the modal meaning of obligation, which is absent in the original text, can be the following fragment: Reaching our sustainable development goals means organizing ourselves better. Let there be no more walls or boxes; no more ministries or agencies working at cross purposes.

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